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Chemical Constituents of *Eupatorium riparium* Regel¹

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TERPENES, sterols and flavonoids are known to occur in various species of *Eupatorium*; a common genus of the family Asteraceae (Compositae). Recently we reported the occurrence of a new triterpene epoxy lupeol², lupeol, β -amyrin and a flavone salvigenin³ from *Eupatorium odoratum*^{2,3} and eupacannol, a novel pentacyclic triterpene alcohol with a rearranged ursane skeleton from *Eupatorium cannabinum*⁴, both species being collected from Darjeeling. In continuation of our studies on Indian *Eupatorium* species we undertook the chemical investigation of an Indian variety of *Eupatorium riparium* Regel collected from Shillong in the Sub-Himalayan region of north-east India. Earlier workers reported chromenes from the Australian⁵ as well as Jamaican⁶ variety of the same plant. The present study has revealed the occurrence of taraxasteryl palmitate [urs-20(30)-en-3- β -ol-hexadecanoate: second natural occurrence] as the major product (0.09%) along with taraxasterol (0.01%), stigmasterol (0.02%) and two uncharacterised compounds — an unsaturated liquid hydrocarbon (0.04%) and a microcrystalline solid fatty alcohol (0.02%), m.p. 84-86°.

The light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract of the whole plant of *E. riparium* was chromatographed over silica gel, using solvents of increasing polarity.

Evaporation of the light petroleum eluted fraction furnished an oily residue (two distinct spots in TLC) which could be resolved into a colourless liquid *L* (yield 0.04%) and a crystalline compound *I* (yield 0.09%) upon repeated chromatographies over silica gel.

Compound *I* crystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless needles, m.p. 102-03°, $[\alpha]_D +70^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.77); analysed for C₄₆H₈₀O₂ (M⁺ 664) and showed positive TNM colouration; ν_{\max}^{KBr} 1722 cm⁻¹ (CO), 1633 (C=C), 863 (=CH₂ out-of-plane bending); PMR (60 MHz, CDCl₃) (δ) 2.27 (2H ill-defined *t*, *J* ~ 6Hz, CH₂CH₂COOR), 4.60 (2H, *m*, C=CH₂), 4.45 (1H, *m*, HCOCOR, the low field component buried under the C=CH₂ signal). From the above IR and PMR data *I* was suggested to be an ester. Saponification of *I* by treatment with 5% KOH solution in tetrahydrofuran-methanol(1:1) at room temperature, followed by usual work up, furnished an acid *A* and a triterpene alcohol *II*. The acid *A*, crystallised from aqueous ethanol, had m.p. 64°, C₁₆H₃₂O₂ (M⁺256); $[\alpha]_D \pm \theta^\circ$; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1690 cm⁻¹ (CO); weak absorption at 1375 cm⁻¹ indicates minimum substitution⁷; PMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) (δ) 2.29 (2H, *t*, *J* = 7Hz, RCH₂CH₂COOH), a broad singlet at δ 1.26 is assignable to protons of (CH₂)_{*n*} indicating the presence of a methylene chain. *A* was identified to be palmitic acid by its mass spectrometry⁸ showing M - 43 peak (expulsion of C₂, C₃, C₄ and 1H) and other characteristic peaks at *m/e* (M - 43 - 14*n*) and *m/e* (41 + 14*n*) where *n* = 0, 1, 2, 3... with the decrease of relative intensities as *n* increases, a characteristic of straight chain fatty acid. It was further confirmed by comparison of the GLC curve of its methyl ester (obtained by methylation of *A* with BF₃ in methanol) with that of an authentic sample of methyl palmitate.

I, R = OCO.(CH₂)₁₄CH₃
II, R = H
III, R = COCH₃

The alcohol *II*, showing positive Liebermann-Burchardt colouration for triterpenes, crystallised from light petroleum-benzene (1:1) as colourless needles, m.p. 218-19°, C₃₀H₅₀O (M⁺426), $[\alpha]_D +91^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.76); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3380 cm⁻¹ (OH), 1655 (C=C), 870 (=CH₂ out-of-plane bending); positive TNM colouration: PMR (60 MHz, CHCl₃) (δ) 0.76, 0.86, 0.90, 0.97, 1.03 and 1.09 (21H, seven methyls on saturated carbons), 4.60 (2H, *m*, C=CH₂), 3.22 (1H, ill-defined *q*, *J*_{ax-ax} ~ 9Hz, *J*_{ax-eq} ~ 5Hz, CHOH (axial)). *II* formed an acetate *III*, m.p. 243-44°, C₃₂H₅₂O₂ (M⁺468); $[\alpha]_D +107^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.67); Sarett oxidation of *II* with CrO₃/Py afforded *IV*, m.p. 180-81°. $[\alpha]_D +127^\circ$ (CHCl₃, *c* 0.69): All these data and the mass fragmentation pattern⁹ of *II* (important ion peaks at *m/e* 411, 408, 357, 344, 315,

NOTES

207, 189, 136, 135, 109, 107° indicated it to be taraxasterol¹⁰. Final confirmation was received by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR spectra) of II, III and IV with the corresponding authentic samples⁹.

Characterisation of A and II admitted compound I as taraxasteryl palmitate [urs-20(30)en-3 β -ol hexadecanoate]. A thorough literature survey indicated that this is the second report of the natural occurrence of taraxasteryl palmitate which was earlier reported¹¹ only recently.

Light petroleum-benzene (1 : 1) eluate fractions of the main chromatogram, after evaporation, afforded a gummy residue which upon repeated chromatography over silica gel furnished a fatty alcohol, crystallised from light petroleum as a micro-crystalline solid, m.p. 84-86° (yield 0.02%) and a triterpene crystallising from light petroleum-benzene mixture (1 : 1) as colourless needles, m.p. 218-19° (yield 0.01%) characterised as taraxasterol (II) by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC, superimposable IR spectra with an authentic sample).

Evaporation of the benzene eluate fractions of the main chromatogram yielded a gummy residue which upon purification through repeated chromatography afforded a sterol (yield 0.02%) crystallising from light petroleum as colourless needles, m.p. 160-61°. This was found to be identical with stigmasterol by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-TLC, IR).

The liquid *L* (R_f 0.7, silica gel G, light petroleum) with a maximum impurity of 2% as shown in the GLC analysis showed positive TNM colouration. ν_{\max} (KBr) 2950 cm^{-1} , 2880 (C-H), 1635 (C=C) indicated it to be an unsaturated hydrocarbon; comparatively strong absorption band at 1375 cm^{-1} is assignable to a large number of methyl substituents⁷. Further study on compound *L* and the fatty alcohol, m.p. 84-86° are in progress.

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Pd(II) Complexes of N,N'-Substituted Thioureas

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Pd(II) complexes of some N-aryl, N'-2(5-halo pyridyl) thioureas were prepared. IR studies reveal that the complexes formed have 1 : 2 metal to ligand ratio. The metal is linked to the ligands through sulphur of thiocarbonyl group.

Experimental

All reagents used were either of B. D. H. or S. MERK Analar grade. The complexes were prepared by adding 0.01M soln. of PdCl₂ (in butanol) slowly and with constant stirring to a hot solution (0.25M) of N-Phenyl, N'-2-(5-Chloro-pyridyl) thiourea, (PCT); N-Phenyl N'-2-(5-Bromo-pyridyl) thiourea, (PBT); N-phenyl, N'-2-(5-Iodo-pyridyl) thiourea, (PIT); N-O-tolyl-2-(5-Chloro-pyridyl) thiourea, (TCT); or N-O-tolyl, N'-2-(5-Bromo-pyridyl) thiourea, (TBT); or N-O-tolyl, N'-2-(5-Iodo-pyridyl) thiourea (TIT) in butanol. The complex got precipitated immediately. It was filtered, washed with butanol and then dried in an air at 60-70°.

The composition of complexes was determined by estimation of the elements N, S, Cl and Pd by standard methods. Conductance measurements were made on a conductivity meter, type LBR, WTW, Germany, using a dip type cell. IR in KBr were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Grating IR Spectrophotometer (Model 237-8).

Results and Discussion

The complexes of PCT, PBT and TCT were reddish in colour whereas that of PIT and PBT were light yellow. They were found soluble in CHCl₃ and CCl₄ but were insoluble in ethanol, butanol, water and ether.

The composition of these complexes on the basis of elemental analysis, could be represented by the general formula PdCl₂L₂, where L is the appropriate substituted thiourea.